

Please cite this report as:

Nangle, B., & Ratti, G. (2026). *A Cross-Country Analysis of Extreme Political Discourse and Its Media Circulation*. KU Leuven, Leuven: DEMINE.

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DEMINE is supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe (HORIZON) Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Doctoral Networks (MSCA-DN), under Grant Agreement no 101167978.

A Cross-Country Analysis of Extreme Political Discourse and Its Media Circulation

Work package 3 – Deliverable 3.4

Submission date: April 30, 2026

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1. Executive Summary

Responding to DEMINE's core research goal of identifying and analysing extreme discourse related to migration at the intersections of politics, media, and interpersonal communication, this report maps the transnational mechanisms through which far-right narratives are produced, circulated, and normalised across digital platforms. This report provides a cross-country analysis of extreme political discourse, focusing on the transnational dynamics through which far-right narratives are produced, circulated, and normalised across digital platforms. The comparison between Belgium and Italy illustrates how similar transnational far-right patterns are adapted to nationally specific political debates, migration histories, and identity narratives. Drawing on empirical research conducted within the DEMINE project, a scoping review of the broader literature on extreme discourse, and case studies from the focal countries, indicated alongside analysis of the transnational anglophone far-right digital ecosystem, the report maps the mechanisms through which nationally specific grievances are rendered interchangeable within a shared civilisational ideological frame.

Based on the scoping review and the analysis of selected far-right digital materials, including Instagram Reels and national case-study examples from Belgium and Italy, the report identifies three main interconnected processes through which transnational far-right meta-communities are constructed and sustained. "Transnationalisation" describes the design of ideological content intended to resonate across national borders through identity frames centred on "Europe" or "Western civilisation." "Translocalisation" describes the adaptation of that content to specific national contexts through sockpuppet accounts, serial misattribution of footage, and the overlay of locally specific cues on externally produced material, manufacturing the appearance of organic grassroots sentiment. "Transmythologisation" describes the construction of a coherent civilisational imaginary across time, binding mythologised pasts, dystopian representations of the present, and projected futures into a single narrative of civilisational decline and potential restoration.

The report further examines how gendered representations function as an affective infrastructure within this ecosystem, as a vessel for gender misinformation and manipulation that characterise much of this extreme discourse. Analysis of far-right Instagram Reels drawn from the transnational anglophone far-right ecosystem documents how stable archetypes of approved and disapproved femininity and masculinity norms and frames operate as portable semiotic templates, attached to emergent events to produce emotional resonance and ideological coherence across national contexts. Femonationalist and homonationalist framings, in which protection discourses and selective invocations of gender or LGBTQ+ rights serve as vehicles for racist exclusion, are shown to operate across both nationally specific party-political formations and the broader transnational digital far right.

These findings are situated within the broader methodological landscape identified by the DEMINE scoping review, which documents significant patterns and conceptual fragmentation across the literature on extreme discourse and highlights the underrepresentation of multimodal analytical approaches relative to the communicative complexity of contemporary far-right digital culture.

The report concludes with recommendations for researchers, platform regulators and counter-extremism practitioners. Key priorities include the development of more integrative cross-national analytical frameworks, regulatory attention to translocalisation and content monetisation infrastructures, and counter-narrative strategies attuned to the affective and aesthetic rather than purely propositional dimensions of far-right recruitment.

2. About DEMINE

DEMINE goals

Globalisation and immigration have altered intercommunity relations, leading to a rise in intergroup conflict marked by discrimination against diverse minorities. This has given way to various forms of radicalisation and extremism, spanning religious, political, and xenophobic spectrums worldwide. Globalisation and immigration strain social cohesion (shared public values, group norms, guiding principles) in numerous countries. While individual attitudes may not have shifted significantly, the prominence of migration in public discourse and the polarisation of public opinion have increased substantially. As a result, a divided public opinion has become more overtly hostile towards migration.

The DEMINE (DEaling with conflicts related to MIgration: NEgotiating social cohesion through communication) European Joint Doctorate (DN-JD) network is a collaborative effort across disciplines. Its primary goal is to enhance Europe's capacity to address a significant challenge: the rise of various forms of radicalisation and extremism that pose a threat to social cohesion. Through a combination of inter-sectoral mobility and a balanced blend of research and transferable competences, DEMINE develops a much-needed framework on the role and interplay of interpersonal and mediated communication in intergroup relations and conflict related to migration and globalisation, ultimately contributing to social cohesion. DEMINE has crafted a comprehensive research and training programme to examine the complex relationships between various forms of communication, including traditional media, social media, and interpersonal interactions. This programme aims to understand how various communication channels shape individual attitudes and beliefs regarding migration, as well as their impact on intergroup dynamics (social cohesion), especially within the broader context of political and societal polarisation, and the processes of radicalisation, with a specific focus on migration-related aspects.

DEMINE Educational Goals

- Train nine doctoral candidates to become the next generation of interdisciplinary researchers skilled in digital methods, participatory community research, and the evaluation of intergroup conflicts.
- Equip candidates with advanced theoretical and practical knowledge, focusing on strategic analysis, community-based participatory youth work, and open-source intelligence techniques.
- Develop transferable skills such as self-management, inter-sectoral collaboration, and innovation-oriented thinking to prepare candidates for both academic and non-academic careers.
- Promote interdisciplinary and international mobility, enabling candidates to apply their research findings in real-world contexts and contribute to professional fields ranging from strategic analysis to media production.

DEMINE Research Goals

- Identify and analyse the differences and similarities across various forms of socially unacceptable, extreme discourse, particularly related to migration, at the intersections of politics, media, and interpersonal communication.
- Investigate the impact of extreme discourse on individual attitudes and beliefs, with a specific focus on adolescents and vulnerable populations, while understanding the socio-demographic and psychological factors influencing susceptibility.
- Develop countermeasures to empower adolescents, news media producers and political actors to mitigate the societal impact of divisive discourse, fostering social cohesion and reinforcing democratic principles.

- Provide a nuanced, cross-cultural, and interdisciplinary understanding of the mechanisms of polarization and radicalization to inform effective strategies and policy interventions.

By integrating these educational and research goals, DEMINE aims to enhance Europe's capacity to address the growing societal challenges linked to migration, fostering resilience and inclusivity in an increasingly polarized world.

DEMINE Consortium

DEMINE consists of three academic partners namely, Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Aarhus Universitet, and Università Degli Studi di Padova, as well as nine non-academic partners including OCAM-OCAD, City of Mechelen, Textgain, The Migration Policy Group, Refugees Welcome, Institut for Menneskerettigheder, Stichting Bellingcat, Verwey-Jonker Institute, and Hannah Arendt Institute.

The DEMINE consortium will train nine doctoral candidates (DCs) within a cross-disciplinary and international environment, giving them the opportunity to network, study and collect data in Western, Northern, Southern and Eastern Europe (see secondments) in collaboration with academic and non-academic experts, with ample opportunities to develop transferable skills such as technology literacy, adaptability (i.e., not feeling helpless in the face of change), strong communication skills, and ability to work in a team, in a dependable and well-organised fashion.

3. Introduction

This report provides a cross-country mapping of extreme political discourse, analysing variations and commonalities across different nations. It examines the prevalence, characteristics, and impact of extremist narratives within political dialogues in the DEMINE focal countries, with a particular focus on migration related discourse. The analysis explores how these discourses are framed, their traction among the population, and the socio-political contexts that either exacerbate or mitigate their spread. Additionally, the report evaluates the role of media and digital platforms in disseminating these narratives, identifying key patterns and trends. This comprehensive mapping is grounded in a DEMINE scoping review of the extreme discourse literature, multimodal discourse analysis of 2,602 far-right Instagram Reels drawn from the transnational anglophone ecosystem, and case study material from the DEMINE focal countries of Belgium and Italy, and serves as a foundation for understanding the DEMINE landscape of extreme political discourse and offers insights into effective strategies for addressing and countering these trends at both national and international levels.

4. Data and Methods

This report draws on three empirical sources. First, a scoping review of the literature on extreme discourse that indicates the dehumanisation and framing of migration and migrants as an existential threat to national identity values and cultures as part of the DEMINE project (WP1), which explored existing research on discursive patterns and contexts¹.

Second, a multimodal discourse analysis of 2,602 Instagram Reels drawn from prominent transnational anglophone far-right profiles. Third, case study material from the DEMINE focal countries of Belgium and Italy, examining far-right party manifestos, campaign materials, and social media content to document nationally specific articulations of the transnational patterns identified across the broader dataset. The analysis primarily draws on anglophone far-right content, which functions as the dominant operational language of transnational far-right discourse; the Belgian and Italian case studies ground the analysis in nationally specific contexts, ensuring consistency across the report's cross-national scope.

The Instagram component employed researcher-created personas interacting with the platform's recommendation system over time, beginning with seed content identified through hashtag searches and following the recursive logic of algorithmic amplification. By the point of thematic saturation, nearly all algorithmically delivered content consisted of far-right or far-right-adjacent material — a finding that itself speaks to Instagram's role as an amplification infrastructure rather than a neutral host. This methodological approach responds to a gap identified by the DEMINE scoping review: multimodality remains under-theorised and inconsistently operationalised across the extreme discourse literature, with most studies continuing to privilege textual interpretation even when nominally engaging with visual or audiovisual material. The present study's multimodal discourse analysis directly addresses this gap, attending to how short-form video produces meaning through the interplay of text, image, sound, and affective register simultaneously.

¹ The scoping review focused on academic literature addressing migration-related extreme discourse, far-right communication, and platformed political narratives across transnational contexts. It was used to identify recurring patterns, relevant actors, and platform dynamics as part of DEMINE (WP1) The scoping review was conducted in collaboration with the wider DEMINE consortium. The authors gratefully acknowledge the contributions of doctoral candidates and supervisors across the network whose collective efforts produced the evidence base on which this report draws.

5. Discursive Patterns in Migration Narratives

Migration discourse across Europe is structured by recurring patterns that shape how migrants are framed within political and media discourse. Building on this context, the DEMINE scoping review examines far-right attitudes towards migration by identifying significant anti-immigration content circulating online through political campaigns, posters, and audience engagement. The scoping review, understood here as the project's preliminary DEMINE mapping of recurring migration-related literature, illustrates discursive patterns in which dehumanising rhetoric is used to diminish migrants through negative and stereotyped visual representations. In campaigns and social media posts, these representations serve as strategies to stimulate hate speech and violent narratives among audiences (Ali, 2025; Wahlström et al., 2021). This method of portrayal has been demonstrated by the public as well as several far-right parties in the European context, such as Lega Nord in Italy, Vlaams Belang in Belgium, and AfD in Germany, among many others, which use visuals alongside text to dehumanise migrants. Empirical studies on visual politics have also shown how AfD imagery in Germany misuses LGBT and women's bodies as dehumanising tools within anti-immigration discourse.

Observations have also identified a predominant element within the scoping review, suggesting that “us vs them” is a dominant factor in the construction and circulation of far-right content. The exemplification of nationalist discourse in Italy has been seen through Matteo Salvini's lexicon, which portrays immigrants as dangerous and dishonest to Italian traditional values. A significant pattern within an “us vs them” rhetoric in the Italian context is the emphasis, by Lega Nord, on Italy's cultural vulnerability, where immigrants are a persistent threat towards individuals through violence and disorder (Venanzetti et al., 2026). This factor demonstrates how the Italian far-right party stresses in picturing immigrants as deviant towards Italian citizens rather than Italian culture. Such rhetorical construction, as demonstrated in the literature and in the DEMINE scoping review, illustrates a persistent mechanism within migration narrative constructions.

The scoping review further identifies several recurring discursive clusters relevant to the material examined, including explicitly dehumanising and othering expressions, threat and fear-framings, and what it terms “accusation in the mirror” strategies. In the context of the scoping review analysis, accusation in the mirror refers to a discursive mechanism through which targeted groups are represented as already doing, or intending to do, the very harm that is being projected onto them. In other words, migrant or racialised groups are portrayed as the source of harm to others, which can then be used to justify exclusionary, hostile, or defensive responses against them. These mechanisms identified in the review analysis are rarely treated in isolation; dehumanisation frequently co-occurs with threat framing and affectively charged moral language, in which visual frames operate as a structuring principle across otherwise distinct discursive formations (Marcks et al., 2022; Maricut-Akbik, 2021). Therefore, migrant women have often been instrumentalised by far-right groups and ideologies through discursive patterns that reflect accusation in the mirror, particularly when they are framed as symbols of victimhood, danger, or social threat within anti-migration narratives in the media.

It is also essential to further understand the actors and forms of agency through which such narratives are reproduced, adapted, and made locally resonant across digital spaces through methodology and operations. The transnational aspect of media circulation has been demonstrated to operate across online borders. Understanding discursive patterns helps analyse how media circulate organically, translocally, and transnationally across online communities, forums, and platforms. The report investigates the movement of extreme political discourse across countries within the DEMINE landscape.

6. Women's bodies as devices in transnational far-right discourse

The analysis of gendered representations in far-right discourse draws on and responds to a pattern identified in the DEMINE alongside the scoping review (WP1): gender-sensitive perspectives, while present in the broader literature on extreme discourse, remain an emergent and underrepresented

conceptual lens relative to the volume of content warranting such analysis. The investigation that follows examines how these mechanisms are specifically articulated through gendered misrepresentation and disinformation in the representation of migrant women's bodies, a combination that the existing literature has addressed only partially and that the DEMINE focal countries of Belgium, Italy, and the transnational anglophone far right make visible in distinct but interconnected ways.

Studies have demonstrated how far-right discourse circulates through transnational digital platforms; however, further analysis is needed on how these narratives are structured through gendered representations, particularly the symbolic deployment of migrant women's bodies in online propaganda (Doerr, 2021). Drawing on case studies from the DEMINE focal countries of Italy and Belgium, this section examines how representations function as a discursive tool through which far-right actors frame, weaponise, and politicise migration.

The instrumentalisation of female bodies as a tactic has been used within extreme far-right propaganda online and offline to disseminate hate speech through symbolism of political framing. An offline example produced by the Belgian far-right party Vlaams Belang was their 2012 campaign poster depicting a white woman wearing a burka, half naked, with the slogan "Freedom or Islam? Dare to choose!" (see Appendix A1). This is a classic illustration of how political parties construct narratives through symbols such as the burka vs the bikini, which imply a 'us vs them' discourse (Mostowska, 2021). Additionally, women's freedom as a Western feminist concept of freedom has often been incorrectly utilised for the dehumanisation of non-Western migrant women, further promoting anti-gender within an anti-immigration lens through visual and symbolic elements (Doerr, 2021). The appropriation of women's rights language or so-called femonationalism indicates the further appropriation of the female body and the meanings it carries as a device in shaping discourse. The pattern of burka vs bikini has appeared on multiple occasions within the Vlaams Belang in Belgium, and within the AfD far-right party ads in Germany.

Vlaams Belang, for instance, as a far-right organisation, in the 2024–2025 manifesto, continued its anti-immigration agenda, calling for "Stop islamisering" (Vlaams Belang, 2024). This is significant within the political spectrum as narratives have been built and programmed using female bodies as a discursive weapon to further articulate their political manifesto. This rationale has also been identified within the Italian far-right political organisation, the Northern League, which posted on their Instagram page on the 8th of March 2026, "... in Italy no woman should feel obliged to cover herself with a niqab, burqa, or any other garment that nullifies her identity and dignity." (Lega Nord Instagram, 2026). The party used an online visual representation of a Muslim woman alongside their statement to build a narrative of women's liberation through victim framing (Sposito, E. et al., 2025). Hence, such communication utilises migrant women's bodies and symbols as discursive battlegrounds in online spaces.

Therefore, victim framing circulation is also highlighted in the Fratelli d'Italia 2024 manifesto, where the party mentions "... women are deprived of their freedom and dignity because of the culture of their country of origin." (Fratelli D'Italia, 2024). This type of rhetoric suggests that Muslim women lack freedom, and helping them should be an Italian duty to combat gender-based violence. This shows that the manufacture of visual propaganda utilised in campaigns is embedded in programme texts through political manifestos in transnational scenarios in Belgium and Italy. Therefore, this illustration of genderised propaganda construction and circulation is tied to the operationalisation of extreme discourse through political architectures. On that account, female bodies are part of such an infrastructure that allows narratives to be manufactured and moved between organisations, platforms and countries through diverse methods.

This phenomenon can be understood within the broader dynamics of transnational far-right communication, where gendered representations function within shared symbolic repertoires (Nangle

& d'Haenens, under review). Building this argument further, the AI-generated character “Amelia” reflects a new wave of far-right memetic propaganda, in which the female body is symbolically instrumentalised and synthetically produced as a portable memetic device for nationalist and supremacist narratives (Quin, 2025). Amelia is a video game AI avatar funded by the British Home Office as an anti-extremism character. However, she became a far-right pop star, showing up on multiple platforms. Her videos on X feature extreme discourse appealing to a younger crowd, as Amelia is a young goth schoolgirl (see appendix A2). The portrayal of her body as a symbol of national identity, freedom, and belonging, evokes a sense of safety vs danger. In this case, it is possible to argue that Amelia, as a character, is a replicable format that can be inserted and manipulated in multiple contexts, rather than a static image, in contrast to older forms of propaganda circulation. Furthermore, the significance of Amelia's age suggests the aim of targeting younger groups susceptible to its persuasion, indicating that such media circulation goals are to recruit.

Amelia's metapolitical aesthetics resonate with an image of a saviour in which her ideological message is embedded with family values and the innocence of the white woman, an image often used by 'tradwives' posts (Tebaldi, 2024). Consequently, this factor stimulates seductive imagery of the ideal Western woman, embodying values that appeal to a wider online community (see Appendix A2). On 'X', a group called 'Women's Safety Initiative', with a significant number of Amelia's supporters, has spread her videos as a British national hero, using them as an operational communication device. Amelia's figure is portrayed as a symbolic feature of meta-community engagement as far-right propaganda. This illustrates how meta-communities are built to function and appeal to a public through narratives, symbols and bodies within the context of AI-generated propaganda. On the other hand, Italy's far right has also explored the use of AI propaganda through victim framing, as Lega Nord leader Matteo Salvini published several Facebook posts in 2025 (Tondo, 2025), often portraying women as being threatened by refugees or Muslim girls as being abused by their own parents. This further shows Italy's far-right groups' attempts to use anti-immigration and Islamophobic framing that utilises the female body as a vessel, contrary to the UK, which promotes Amelia's metapolitical aesthetic. This type of post is projected to look locally significant, indicating a translocal element of media circulation.

As seen above, the system employed by the far-right is not an isolated case but an online system and methodology that can be interpreted as a transnational *modus operandi* in Europe showing common patterns, objects and symbols that belong to an ideological format of media manipulation and circulation. Female bodies are part of a symbolic repertoire sustaining the transnational meta-community's media engagement. This tactic further demonstrates that the female body itself is a site of power used through an online infrastructure that carries anti-gender ideology that is feasibly manipulative and codable (Grabowska, 2022). Using the word "codable" is significant for comprehending the instrumentalisation of the body through visual methods within AI-generated material.

7. Far-Right Transnationalism and Translocalism

Far-right political discourse has undergone a significant transformation in the digital era. What were once geographically bounded movements, shaped by national political cultures and constrained by the limits of physical organisation, have become increasingly transnational in character, sustained by shared symbolic repertoires, platform infrastructures, and participatory digital cultures that enable ideological content to travel rapidly across national contexts. This shift has significant implications for how extreme discourse is analysed, monitored, and countered.

This process can be observed in the recurring use of burka and veiling imagery across far-right parties, highlighting this transnational aspect, which can also be relevant within transnational meta-communities as a symbolic repertoire (Öztürk et al. 2022). In both German and Italian contexts, far-right actors have used visual contrasts between unveiled and veiled women to frame Islam and migration

as threats to women's freedom, national identity, and European values. Although these images are adapted to specific national audiences, they rely on shared symbolic elements. This illustrates how similar anti-migration narratives circulate transnationally while appearing locally grounded in different political and cultural contexts throughout digital spaces.

A key mechanism driving this transformation is what this report terms the construction of a transnational meta-community: a fluid, digitally-mediated formation held together not by formal organisational ties but by shared symbols, narratives, aesthetic conventions, and affective orientations (Lamour, 2020). Within this formation, nationally specific grievances, around migration, cultural change, economic precarity, and perceived elite betrayal, are rendered interchangeable through adaptable ideological templates that can be localised for specific national audiences while retaining their core civilisational logic. This process of translocalisation allows content produced in one national context to register as authentically local in another, manufacturing the appearance of organic, grassroots sentiment across disparate publics.

A central mechanism through which translocalisation operates is the deployment of pseudonymous "faux-local" accounts, or sockpuppets (Paterson, 2024), that obscure actors' true geographic or ethnic positionality while performing the role of local citizens. Such identities simulate authenticity, allowing external actors to intervene in domestic political discourse by manufacturing the appearance of grassroots engagement (Chan, 2024; da Rosa Lazarotto, 2023; Kovic et al., 2018). This practice aligns with broader research on disinformation infrastructures, which documents how transnational networks use faux-local propaganda and fake local news outlets to influence domestic debates while presenting coordinated content as organic public opinion (Alliance for Securing Democracy, 2024; Glicker & Watts, 2021; O'Keeffe, 2024).

Research on influence operations has shown how foreign actors routinely pose as local activists, using fabricated identities and targeted content to embed polarising narratives within ostensibly domestic information environments. Studies of Russian Internet Research Agency operations demonstrate how state-linked actors deployed faux-local accounts to circulate divisive political messaging by simulating grassroots engagement (Howard et al., 2018). Comparable practices have been identified among other state actors: the Israeli Ministry of Diaspora Affairs reportedly funded an influence operation using AI-generated content and networks of inauthentic accounts to circulate Islamophobic narratives to audiences in the United States and Canada (Middle East Monitor, 2024). Similar dynamics are evident in far-right mobilisation around national contexts: analysis of social media traffic found that slogans such as "Ireland is full" and "Irish lives matter" were more frequently posted by accounts based in the US and UK than by Irish users, indicating the external amplification of ostensibly local nationalist discourse (Gallagher, 2023). Across these cases, fabricated profiles and appeals to imagined local authenticity function as mechanisms of translocalisation, allowing externally produced ideological content to appear domestically rooted.

Such practices now operate at scale through vast networks of fake, bot, and sockpuppet accounts capable of shaping political discourse across platforms (Avaaz, 2019; Robins-Early, 2022; University of Oxford, 2021), and have become increasingly professionalised and commercially driven, with actors monetizing anti-migrant and Islamophobic content through platform advertising systems and generative AI to maximise reach and revenue (The Bureau of Investigative Journalism, 2025). Crisis moments intensify these dynamics: following the Bondi Beach terrorist attack on the 14th of December 2025 in Sydney, Australia, racist and antisemitic falsehoods spread rapidly online, including via newly established fake news websites designed to exploit heightened public attention (Taouk, Workman, & Hair, 2025). A rare moment of infrastructural visibility emerged in 2025 when X briefly introduced its "About This Account" feature, which surfaced users' likely base countries through platform metadata, exposing numerous high-follower MAGA and "America First" accounts as being operated from outside

the United States while performing American or European nationalist identity, a pattern documented through the compilation of foreign-run sockpuppet accounts engaged in pro-Trump and white supremacist propaganda (Reichwingwatch, 2025).

The analysis focuses primarily on anglophone far-right content due to the functionality of English as a shared language for transnational far-right communication across platforms. This allows the report to trace cross-border narrative circulation, while the Belgian and Italian case studies show how these narratives are adapted to national contexts.

8. Transnational Meta-Community Formation: Three Interconnected Mechanisms

Transnationalisation refers to the design and circulation of messaging intended to resonate across national borders while preserving ideological coherence. Far-right actors increasingly operate within a shared discursive ecosystem in which "Europe" or "Western civilisation" functions as a supranational identity frame, allowing content to address audiences across multiple national contexts simultaneously. A concrete example of this shared discursive ecosystem can be observed in the circulation of "remigration" rhetoric as a far-right slogan across European contexts (Shamin, 2025). While the term reproduces a shared ideological logic in which migrants are framed as removable subjects and national belonging is imagined through exclusion. In other words, the policy of "remigration" is advocated by several far-right parties and serves as a transnational discursive template, operating from political language of border and security to a digital tool for anti-immigration narratives.

Translocalisation describes the adaptation of transnational content to specific national or local contexts, producing the appearance of grassroots authenticity. This may occur through sockpuppet accounts simulating local citizenship, the serial misattribution of footage to multiple national contexts, or the overlay of locally specific textual cues on content of external origin. The study documents this across the dataset: the same footage of a racialised assault on public transport, for instance, circulated across multiple Reels claiming the incident had occurred in Scotland, Italy, and Spain respectively. The effect is to embed externally produced ideological content within domestic information environments, complicating attribution and amplifying resonance. The actual prevalence of inauthentic activity almost certainly exceeds what can be empirically observed given platform opacity, but the instances documented are sufficient to establish translocalisation as, in some cases, a deliberate and strategically leveraged phenomenon.

Transhistoricisation is a further dimension of far-right meta-community construction that the summary must account for. Far-right short-form video does not only operate spatially, it also constructs a coherent civilisational imaginary across time, stitching together mythologised pasts, dystopian representations of the present, and utopian or eliminatory futures. Content draws on ancient civilisations, medieval crusader imagery, colonial-era nostalgia, and explicit revisionism around the Second World War, flattening historically and culturally distinct moments into a single narrative of civilisational continuity and decline. This temporal framing presents exclusionary politics as natural, historically inevitable, and restorative rather than radical. Idealised pasts are set against dystopian present-day framings, multiculturalism, migration, and liberal governance depicted as civilisational collapse, and against projected futures in which racial homogeneity is aestheticised as harmonious and orderly, sometimes explicitly through captions accompanying idyllic imagery such as "we deported them all" or "life if we stopped babysitting third worlders."

These dynamics are observable in granular form in two recurring meme formats identified across the dataset. Nostalgic montage Reels deploy sepia-toned archival footage, emotionally charged music, and textual overlays to construct an idealised lost past and frame its loss as a politically actionable grievance, linking mythologised history to contemporary nativist mobilisation through affect and aesthetic continuity. The "Save Europe" format, the most prominent trend in the dataset, combines stylised nature

imagery, classical statuary adapted into ironic "Chad" memes, neo-medieval symbolism, and sped-up Eurodance or nightcore audio to render locally specific grievances interchangeable within a shared civilisational frame, while remixing historical references from classical antiquity to twentieth-century fascism into contemporary meme aesthetics. Both formats maintain plausible deniability through irony and ambiguity while facilitating ideological acculturation.

Comment sections function as a further infrastructural layer in this process. Rather than secondary or reactive spaces, they operate as acculturative environments in which ideological meaning is articulated more explicitly than in the Reels themselves. Dogpiling by coordinated or automated accounts produces the impression of mass consensus; emoji-coded dog whistles, juice box emojis signifying Jews, crescent moon emojis combined with "ancer" to equate Islam with cancer, double lightning bolts referencing the SS insignia, allow overtly extremist content to evade automated moderation; and GIF-based responses, such as a clip from the HBO series Rome deployed as a stand-in for a Nazi salute, enable in-group signalling through aesthetic displacement. Algorithmic presentation of comment sections may further intensify these dynamics by foregrounding ideologically aligned responses and downranking dissent.

Gendered representations constitute a further dimension of this transnational circulation infrastructure. Empirical analysis of far-right Instagram Reels drawn from the anglophone transnational ecosystem documents how femininities and masculinities function as affective anchors through which ideological content acquires emotional salience and cross-border resonance (Nangle & d'Haenens, under review-b). Stable gendered archetypes, endangered white women, racialised male threats, betrayed protectors, disciplined tradwives, circulate as portable semiotic templates that can be attached to emergent incidents across national contexts, allowing disparate events to be rendered legible through a shared interpretive frame. Gender thus operates not only as ideological content but as affective infrastructure: a mechanism through which the transnational meta-community reproduces coherence across otherwise disparate national grievances.

Building on this argument, the scoping review shows how this dynamic can be observed in the recurring use of women's safety and protection narratives within anti-migration discourse. Across different national contexts, migrant men, for instance, are framed as threats to Western women, while women are positioned as symbols of the nation, cultural vulnerability, and values (Kulz et al. 2025). These representations allow far-right actors to translate broader anti-migration claims into emotionally salient narratives of 'dangerous men'. In this way, gendered imagery helps local incidents appear as evidence of public conflict, reinforcing the gender instrumentalisation within far-right discourse and the circulation of such transnational narratives.

A further mechanism of transnational meta-community formation documented across the dataset is what Nangle and d'Haenens term reactionary newsjacking: the strategic appropriation of viral or viralised incidents to lock interpretations into pre-existing far-right ideological frames (under review-b). Rather than producing original content, far-right actors exploit crisis moments as cognitive openings, seeding extremist interpretations into trending topics to achieve narrative dominance before alternative framings can circulate. The process is recursive: reframings are amplified through transnational networks of influencers, bots, and mirror accounts, and may reach mainstream political figures, after which they feed back into audience worldviews, reinforcing interpretive biases and increasing susceptibility to future iterations. Debunking frequently backfires, functioning as further evidence of elite bias or media conspiracy within self-sealing epistemic logics that neutralise correction. The Charlie Kirk assassination exemplifies this dynamic at the transnational level: European far-right parties rapidly reframed the murder as collective persecution, deploying his death as an organic binder to consolidate cross-border ideological alignment around a shared enemy and a shared struggle. Such cases demonstrate how reactionary newsjacking accelerates affective alignment across nationally distinct movements,

converting discrete incidents into ideological proof within a shared civilisational narrative and reinforcing the meta-community's coherence in real time.

Together, these mechanisms allow the far right to paper over significant political and ideological contradictions between nationally distinct movements, producing surface coherence through shared aesthetics and affect rather than programmatic alignment.

9. Transnational anglophone far-right digital communication

The nationally specific cases examined above operate within, and are amplified by, a broader transnational anglophone far-right digital ecosystem in which gendered representations function as a shared symbolic repertoire. Analysis of 2,602 Instagram Reels drawn from prominent far-right profiles documents how this ecosystem deploys femininities and masculinities as affective infrastructure, a recurring semiotic architecture through which complex social events are simplified into narratives of racialised threat, institutional betrayal, and civilisational decline (Nangle & d'Haenens, under review-b).

Across this corpus, approved femininities cluster around several recurring archetypes. The hypersexualised or conventionally attractive white woman aestheticises whiteness as desirable and worth defending. The "tradwife" figure frames domesticity and maternal virtue as resistance to modernity and feminist "degeneracy." A third, more explicitly racialised form, drawing on Viking, Celtic, and Slavic visual motifs, fuses erotic appeal with heritage and racial purity into what the study terms a "mythic-erotic" femininity, aestheticising racial identity as a civilisational fantasy. Nostalgic images of Iranian women before the 1979 revolution or Afghan women prior to Taliban rule circulate as cautionary femonationalist evidence, framing Western civilisation as uniquely protective of women's freedom while legitimising anti-Muslim racism. These approved femininities collectively function as symbols of what must be protected or restored, rendering exclusionary politics as care.

Disapproved femininities serve as their moral foil. Feminist and left-wing women are caricatured as hypocritical, unattractive, or hysterical. Muslim women are rendered as either fanatical or pitiable. Black women are subject to a recurring "loudmouth" trope that functions as shorthand for racialised disorder. White women in interracial relationships are framed as "race traitors," their autonomy pathologised as civilisational corruption. Together, these constructions naturalise racial and patriarchal hierarchies of feminine value, disciplining women into ideologically sanctioned roles.

Femonationalist and homonationalist logics structure how these representations are attached to emergent events. Sexual violence incidents are instrumentalised to depict immigrants or Muslims as existential threats, with women's suffering mobilised as moral evidence within broader ideological arguments rather than engaged with on its own terms. Homonationalist framings selectively invoke LGBTQ+ rights to stigmatise Muslims as culturally backward, converting queerness into a civilisational alibi for exclusion. In both cases, protection discourses mask xenophobia, as the study documents across cases including anti-asylum hotel narratives, grooming gang moral panics, and newsjacked incidents of alleged migrant violence.

This analysis connects the nationally-specific dynamics documented in the Belgian and Italian cases to a transnational discursive formation in which gendered representations travel across borders as portable ideological templates. The female body functions not only as a site of domestic political contestation but as a node within a transnational symbolic repertoire, one that sustains meta-community coherence through shared aesthetic and affective conventions rather than formal organisational ties.

10. Conclusion and Recommendations

Contemporary far-right discourse does not respect national borders, and analytical and policy frameworks that treat it as primarily a domestic phenomenon will consistently underestimate both its scale and its resilience. The transnational meta-community model described in this report suggests several priorities.

For researchers, cross-national comparative work needs to attend not only to ideological content but to the aesthetic and affective mechanisms through which that content travels, memetic formats, platform affordances, and participatory comment cultures that reinforce ideological acculturation across national contexts. Transhistoricisation deserves particular analytical attention: the way far-right communication binds mythologised pasts, dystopian presents, and projected futures into a coherent civilisational narrative is central to how exclusionary politics is normalised and rendered thinkable, and it operates across both spatial and temporal registers simultaneously.

Research attending to the gendered dimensions of this communication is particularly important. Analysis of anglophone Instagram content and DEMINE focal country-specific examples, demonstrates that femininities and masculinities function as affective infrastructure, stable semiotic templates that are repeatedly attached to emergent events to produce ideological coherence and emotional resonance across national contexts (Nangle & d'Haenens, under review-b). Femonationalist and homonationalist framings, in which protection discourses and selective invocations of gender or LGBTQ+ rights serve as vehicles for racist exclusion, operate transnationally and require analytical frameworks that can capture their affective as well as their propositional dimensions. The typology of approved and disapproved femininities and masculinities developed in that study offers one such framework, and its extension to non-anglophone contexts is a priority for future comparative work.

These priorities are reinforced by the DEMINE scoping review (WP1), which finds that the field studying extreme discourse is conceptually rich but significantly fragmented: terminology is empirically grounded but unstandardised across studies, explicit and universally applicable definitions remain rare, and the integration of multimodal analysis, despite growing recognition of its importance, remains uneven and under-theorised. The review identifies a strong alignment between the conceptual lenses researchers adopt and the terminological choices they make, but notes that this coherence does not extend to the level of definitions, creating conditions in which interpretive flexibility allows for context-sensitivity but hinders cumulative knowledge-building. For cross-national comparative work on far-right discourse specifically, this fragmentation is consequential: without greater methodological transparency and more integrative frameworks, findings from nationally or platform-specific studies are difficult to aggregate or compare. The transnational meta-community model developed in this report represents one contribution toward such integration, but its further development requires the kind of terminological and definitional consolidation the scoping review identifies as a field-wide priority.

For platform regulators and policymakers, the translocalisation of far-right content, including sockpuppet activity, serial misattribution of footage, and the monetisation of extremist content through advertising systems and generative AI, represents a coordination and accountability challenge that existing content moderation frameworks, designed around individual pieces of content rather than transnational circulation patterns and financial incentive structures, are poorly equipped to address. Comment sections warrant specific regulatory attention as spaces where more explicit extremist content circulates under cover of reduced moderation scrutiny.

For counter-extremism practitioners, the meta-community model suggests that inoculation and counter-narrative strategies need to account for the affective and aesthetic dimensions of far-right recruitment, not only its propositional content. The specific formats through which this operates, nostalgic montage

Reels, "Save Europe" meme trends, ironic or "edgy" aesthetics that maintain plausible deniability, require responses attuned to the same registers of irony, nostalgia, humour, and emotional resonance, rather than purely propositional rebuttals that engage with explicit ideological claims while leaving the affective infrastructure intact.

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12. Appendices

A. Appendix- Visual Examples of Gendered Far-Right Political Images

A1- Filip Dewinter posing with his daughter An-Sophie Dewinter while presenting a campaign poster at the New Year's reception of the Merksem branch of Vlaams Belang on 4 February 2012. Source: Getty/AFP

A2 - AI-generated “Amelia” visual circulated in anti-Islam and anti-immigration discourse on X. Source: captured by author from an X post by @benonwine. -

<https://x.com/benonwine/status/2015736453003637204> [Accessed 20 March 2026]